

PurPest - developing a sensor system prototype for detecting pests in plants

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Abstract— PurPest is an EU funded project (Horizon Europe, grant ID 101060634) that will develop and demonstrate an innovative sensor system prototype (SSP) that can rapidly detect five different pests during import of plant material and in farmer fields to stop establishment of these pests and to reduce pesticide inputs by at least 50%. This approach is based on detecting specific volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that are released by the pests or infested plants at low concentrations (< ppm). Specific detection of low VOC amounts required the development and combination of several miniaturized technologies into a sensor system prototype (SSP), such as pre-concentrators, micro gas chromatograms (μ -GC), electronic nose arrays and surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) chips. The project is currently conducting controlled plant experiments to collect and identify the VOCs of interest. Machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) will be used to identify any particular VOC patterns that indicate the presence of the target pests. This generated data will then inform the development of the different SSP components, such as pre-concentrators, μ -GC retention layers and sensor coatings. The SSP will require innovative packaging solutions to include several types of sensors. Moreover, the project targets collaborating with other sensor projects, like newly granted EU project, COMPAS. In order to facilitate this interaction, a certain level of standardization for connection of the sensors and electronics will be necessary. The current paper presents a short update on application of coatings and the overall packaging and integration concepts of the SSP. The PurPest project is conducted by a consortium of 18 partners from 10 European countries, with eight universities, six research institutes and four highly innovative SMEs. The project started in January 2023 and will last for 48 months. The website is www.purpest.eu.

Keywords—components, sensors, pesticides.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the ambitious goals of the Farm2Fork strategy is to reduce the use of pesticides in the EU by 50%. The expected increase in plant pests due to climate change and the intensification of food production systems offsets this target. However, the need to control new pest invasions and already established pests in the EU are, in fact, increasing pesticide use. Hence, new tools and methods are needed to prevent new pest entry into Europe, and to use pesticides more efficiently for established pests in farmer's fields.

PurPest aims to exploit the specific volatile organic compounds (VOCs) released by pests or by the plants attacked by certain pests. These VOCs have been studied for many pests, but their use in pest detection has not yet been fully exploited. The PurPest project will harness the release of pest specific VOCs to develop a sensor system prototype (SSP) that detect VOCs and thus identify and locate target pests.

PurPest is currently carrying out extensive plant experiments where 10 host plants are exposed to five different pests. These are done in the greenhouse (for quarantine pests, priority pests and established pests) and in the field (established pests). In the green house experiments environmental conditions are controllably varied. VOC emitted from pests or plants infested with the target pest are collected and analysed to generate a comprehensive database with the chemical signatures of pest specific VOC patterns for the target pest-host systems in our study. This database will be made publicly available via the PurPest community on Zenodo [1].

The SSPs developed in PurPest will detect the chemical signatures identified by the plant experiments. To obtain the required detection limit (<ppb), sensitivity and selectivity, sensor components based on 9 different principles will be studied and developed. The best performing sensor components will be selected for integration into the final SSP and six SSP will be fabricated for detecting target pests at import stations for plant material in the partner countries.

Fig. 1. Overview of the SSP, which components are commercially available, developed in PurPest, or a combination of both.

II. THE SSP

The SSP will contain several sensing technologies integrated into a portable unit that will conduct advanced data analysis to determine the likelihood of an inspected plants to be infested and communicate the result to the user (Fig. 1).

III. SENSING TECHNOLOGIES

The sensing operations are divided into three main categories which will be described in this section: 1) pre-concentration, 2) separation, 3) detection.

A. Preconcentration

The goal of pre-concentration is to increase selectively the concentration of the target VOC before it reaches the sensors, thus lowering the limit of detection (LoD). The project has so far identified two candidate materials that have shown to be good candidates for the expected VOCs; Tanax and CarboTrapX.

B. Separation

The goal of the separation technology is to enable unique identification of the different VOCs during detection. This is usually done using a coil of thin tube with the appropriate retention layer coated on the inside. The length enables the separation of fast and slowly diffusing molecules while the retention layer can be designed to target specific molecules to slow them down even further. Thus, by plotting a detection signal in the time domain, the peaks appearing at different times represent detection of different molecules. This is the principle behind gas and liquid chromatography.

C. Detection

PurPest will investigate the use of several different sensor technologies for the detection of VOCs. Some of the sensing principles require coatings to enhance the sensitivity and/or the selectivity of the detector.

1) Existing commercial technologies

Photo-ionisation detectors (PID) and metal oxide sensors (MOS) already exist in semi-portable GC systems and will be investigated for optimization and utilization. These will serve as a benchmark for the novel sensors developed in the project.

2) Coatings

The sensitivity and selectivity of the proposed SMR and SERS sensors can be increased by orders of magnitude by choosing the most appropriate coatings that are both selective and sensitive to the target volatile.

The partition coefficient, K_p , is a measure of the equilibrium ratio of gas molecules in the polymer and in the gas phase, and the frequency shift of the SMR sensor output is directly proportional to it through the following relationship:

$\Delta f \propto K_p c_g$ where c_g is the concentration of target molecules in the gaseous phase. The partition coefficient K_p in effect adds an amplification factor of between 10 to 1,000 depending upon the solute (i.e. target molecule) and solvent (e.g. polymer). PurPest will develop polymer coatings and investigate a new temperature modulation technique in order use the diffusion-

reaction kinetics to further amplify selectivity and sensitivity of SMR sensors.

Metal organic frameworks (MOFs) are hybrid materials made from inorganic clusters and organic linkers. The possibilities to combine large surface areas, porosity, and functionalities in MOFs have made them attractive in several areas, including sensor technologies such as SERS. Importantly, films can be grown on surfaces as SURMOFs.

3) Electronic nose using SMR sensors

Electronic noses employ an array of non-specific gas sensors as artificial odour receptors. The sensor arrays generate volatile “fingerprints” rather than providing accurate measurements of individual gases. In this project we are developing arrays of surface mounted resonators (SMRs) that operate in the GHz range and detect mass changes at the surface as a change in resonance frequency.

4) Surface enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS)

SERS is a method to enhance the Raman scattering from molecules via “plasmon-mediated amplification of electric fields or chemical enhancement” [2]. In PurPest we are employing two methodologies for this.

The first is using nano-imprint lithography (NIL) of purposefully designed nano-structures that are stamped in a photoresist on a wafer. The pattern is thereby dry etched and covered with a thin layer of gold. These nano-structures enhance the Raman scattering of VOCs that land on the surface. To enhance the effect, the PurPest project is applying the aforementioned coatings.

The second SERS methodology utilizes size & morphology-controlled metal nanosurfaces to accomplish the same effect. The metal multiple layers nanosurfaces are than functionalized for a selective capture of the specific VOCs.

Both SERS surfaces will be measured using the portable Raman spectroscope @Ramascopy, developed by the project partner Saftra Photonics.

IV. SYSTEM INTEGRATION

Sensor integration plays a crucial role for the unified data gathering process and subsequent data analysis. Correct sensor integration requires both mechanical and electrical knowledge of combining different sensor platforms into a unified chamber and extracting the sensor signals in the correct way. Gas sensor technologies are highly sensitive to a number of mechanical issues, such as incorrect sensor placement vs the gas flow, suboptimal choice of surrounding materials increasing gaseous volatile organic compound contamination, airflow fluctuations, insufficient environmental condition monitoring. Similarly electronic signal recording requires a number of techniques to be used to reduce electrical noise and ensure stable gas signal response. The sensor integration needs to be combined with a stable sampler system to ensure each sample is as consistent as possible. All environmental parameters will be recorded to further isolate any condition fluctuations through the data analytics part.

Fig. 2. Picture of Warwick University's μ -GC column and SMR sensor array at the intercomparison campaign at Airmotec.

A. Data analysis

Machine learning analysis will be performed on the recorded sensor signals to build up a sample database and to use that as a reference for VOC analysis done by the plant-pest experts.

V. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

In April 2024 the sensor development partners (Airmotec, Saftra Photonics, Volatile, University of Warwick and SINTEF) were gathered at Airmotec's location in Bordeaux for an intercomparison campaign (Fig. 2). The aim was to test and evaluate newly-developed sensors and detection units. Over the course of the week, we targeted 3 VOC tracers from *Phytophthora ramorum*, the Cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera*) and the Brown marmorated stink bug (*Halyomorpha*

halys). Known gas concentrations of VOCs were generated dynamically using AIRMOTEC's reference devices and monitored with a GC-FID-MS, used as a sensitive reference instrument, allowing to separate, analyse and identify the targeted VOCs. Some potential interferent VOCs were also mixed with the abovementioned VOCs, in order to challenge the sensors and detectors. At the current time the results of the campaign are being analysed. The results will be made public in a project delivery that will be available at the project web site at the end of June, 2024 (www.purpest.eu).

VI. CONCLUSION

The EU project PurPest seeks to develop a portable unit that will sense VOCs at low concentrations to detect potential pest infestation of imported plant material and of crops in the field. Different sensor technologies are being tested and evaluated.

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